

Optimizing QoE for Medical Video Streaming

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Abstract— The present study proposes an adaptive video delivery methodology that enhances quality of experience (QoE) and aids towards the wider adoption of wireless medical video communication systems in standard clinical practice.

I. INTRODUCTION

Video streaming applications have witnessed widespread adoption over the past decades becoming the dominant source of internet traffic. Toward this direction, medical video systems in standard clinical practice are steadily increasing driven by the growing reliability brought on by established and emerging enabling technologies [1]. These technologies can be roughly categorized into video compression algorithms, wired/wireless communication networks, and video quality assessment (VQA) metrics. Medical video applications range from remote diagnosis and care, to 2nd opinion provision and medical education, based on live and/ or on-demand video streaming of different medical video modalities. At the same time, emerging applications invest in the use of tele-operated robots for both diagnosis and surgery, while the use of augmented and extended reality technologies, coupled with 360° video streaming, have the potential to revolutionize medical education and treatment.

A key challenge in live medical applications, such as emergency telemedicine (e.g. from the ambulance) and scenarios that involve low resource settings (e.g., disaster incident sites), is guaranteeing the clinical quality of the communicated video. The latter is a non-trivial process, anchored in the time-varying and error-prone nature of the underlying wireless channels. As such, medical video systems need to adapt to the varying bandwidth throughput supported by the wireless medium, in a timely fashion, while securing the clinical capacity of the transmitted videos. The latter, necessitates adaptive, real-time video encoding and control.

II. METHODOLOGY

Recently, a multi-objective optimization method for adaptive video delivery was proposed by our group [2], [3]. The goal is to maximize video quality and video encoding efficiency while minimizing the associated bitrate demands. For each optimization objective, forward prediction models need to be constructed based on offline training involving a significant number of different video compression instances. To describe our approach, let VQ denote video quality, B_r

denote the bitrate demands, and FPS denote the encoding rate in terms of frames per second. The approach seeks encoding configurations E_n subject to realistic constraints on video quality $VQ \geq VQ_{min}$, bitrate demands $B_r \leq B_{r,max}$, and encoding frame rate $FPS \geq FPS_{min}$, that are optimal in the multi-objective sense given by:

$$\max(VQ(E_n), -B_r(E_n), FPS(E_n)) \quad (1)$$

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach we used real-life network traces of mobile HTTP streaming scenarios over 3G/HSDPA wireless systems [4]. An adaptive controller was then tasked to sense the instantaneous bandwidth variations and trigger an encoding adaptation switch using the generated forward models.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

To generate the models, the leave-one-out approach was employed leveraging an ultrasound dataset composed of 10 videos of the common carotid artery. The proposed method was then compared to the classic adaptive HTTP streaming solution that uses a simple bandwidth selection algorithm to trigger adaptation amongst pre-encoded video instances constructed using the bitrate ladder approach. A number of quality of service and experience (QoS & QoE) metrics were used to demonstrate the performance enhancements of the proposed approach including (i) average video quality using objective VQA metrics such as VMAF and SSIM [2], (ii) number of buffer incidents, (iii) duration of buffer incidents, and (iv) % of buffer level above the panic threshold.

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